

Incorporating Digital Technology in Mathematics Teaching and Learning for Sustainable National Development and Global Competitiveness at Senior Secondary Schools in Oshimili North Local Government Area of Delta State

By

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to incorporate digital technology in the teaching and learning of Mathematics for sustainable national development and global competitiveness at senior secondary school in Oshimili North Local Government Area of Delta State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were raised for the study. The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey. The target population was all the senior secondary schools in Oshimili North educational zone and with a sample size of 180 students which is made up of twenty students each were randomly from each of the nine schools selected for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used in testing the hypotheses. The findings from the study among others indicated that: The lack of availability of digital technology has drastically affected mathematics teaching and learning in educational sector. The study therefore recommended among others that: Digital technology should be used in teacher education and in the professional development of teachers' training and retraining programme; Government should provide the necessary funds to schools for the purchase of digital technology facilities like computer hardware for effective education delivery; The Mathematics teacher should use digital resources like apps, social media etc to keep the class informed about activities and upcoming assignments among others .

Keywords: *Incorporation, Digital Technology, Mathematics, Global Competitiveness*

Introduction

Mathematics is a very important subject that is applied in every fields of study. It is the tool for understanding science, technology and business so it is a force to be reckoned with in the development of any nation and generally been accepted as foundation of science and technology (Okeke, 2019). Mathematics teaching and learning is greatly being influenced by new technologies which in turn influence school curriculum and practices. As mathematics teachers we witness these developing technologies and often wonder whether we are keeping pace with the emerging technologies in teaching and learning. The need for the mathematics teacher to ensure quality lesson delivery cannot be overemphasized. One of the fundamental components of the United Nations sustainable development goals is quality education. It aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Digital technologies have emerged as an essential tool to achieve this goal and ensure sustainability in quality education. The experience of the recent COVID-19 pandemic brought to the fore the need for a paradigm shift in our old classroom practices. As we realized during the schools' lockdown some schools could conveniently go on while some remained locked down without much activities. The schools that keyed into online lessons were schools that were equipped for that. With that experience digital transformation becomes a global imperative in today's world. The mathematics teachers need to understand these technologies as a means of enhancing his lessons and resources and at the same time engage in practices that will provide his students with tools and opportunities to place them in the global map.

The globalization of the world makes it imperative for the mathematics teachers and the students to acquire knowledge and skills that will impact on the society and the nation for sustainable development and global competitiveness. There is a strong consensus that digital technology can improve teaching and learning by motivating students with engaging, interactive and fun learning environment. According to Taylor (2021), digital technology offers new avenues of meaningful communication and collaboration between teachers and students. Digital technology in Mathematics education has to do with introduction of new technology-assisted learning tools such as mobile devices, interactive white boards, smart boards, tablets, laptops, simulations, dynamic visualization and virtual laboratories. Traditional classroom instructions fall short of providing an immediate learning environment, faster evaluations, and more engagement. In contrast, digital learning tools and technology fill this void. With smart phones and other wireless technology devices becoming popular among the general public, it only makes sense that schools and educational institutions make efficient use of them by putting technology in the classroom. According to Haleem et al (2022) integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience, allowing them to remain more interested in the subject without being distracted.

During the pandemic, digital classrooms became the order of the day in order to sustain the education system. Digital classrooms are defined by using electronic devices or platforms such as social media, multimedia and mobile phones to teach students.

With digital technology in Mathematics education, today's educational landscape has altered for the better. Digital learning is a learning strategy that employs technology to fulfill the entire curriculum and allows students to learn quickly and rapidly. The digital classroom entirely focuses on teaching via the use of technology. Students use technological or internet-connected gadgets like laptops, tablets, chrome books etc. Instead of taking notes on what the teacher has taught, most of the curriculum is delivered to students online through an engaging and interactive platform.

Digital technology in the classroom refers to various software and gadgets meant to help students with particular accessibility needs. Digital technology means that devices can be more compact, faster, lighter and more versatile. Huge amounts of knowledge can be stored locally or remotely and moved around virtually immediately. Digital learning is any type of learning that uses technology. Digital learning is defined as any instructional practice that effectively uses technology to strengthen students learning experience and encompasses a wide spectrum of tools and practices. Examples of digital media include soft wares, digital images, digital video, video games, web pages and websites, social media, digital data and data bases, MP3, electronic documents and electronic books.

Global competitiveness as defined by the World Economic Forum (2016) is the ability of a country to achieve sustainable high rates in Gross Domestic Product(GDP) per capita. The international institute for management development defines competitiveness as a field of economic knowledge which analyzes the facts and policies that shaped the ability of a nation to create and maintain an environment that sustains more value creation for its enterprises and more prosperity for its people (Waterford, 2020).

The Global competitiveness report assesses the competitiveness landscape of 131 economies of the world using the Network Readiness Index(NRI). It provides information about the drivers of their productivity and prosperity.

Network Readiness Index (NRI) is one of the leading global indices on the application and impact of information and communication technology (ICT) in economies around the world. In its latest version of 2022, the NRI report maps the network-based readiness landscape of 131 economies based on their performances in four different pillars: Technology, People, Governance and Impact. Each of these pillars is itself comprised of three sub-pillars (see fig II) that have been populated by a total of 58 variables. According to Dutta and Lanvin (2022), the 2022 edition of the NRI focuses on the role of younger generation in leading us into the information age. Recent

trends indicate that future readiness will largely rely on three major currencies: data, talent and learning. The 2022 report showed that the highest ranked economies perform consistently across all dimensions of network readiness, and commit to ensuring that technologies are accessible, affordable and beneficial for the economy and society at large.

Digital Technology is universal in society. There are new demands on educational systems in order to prepare students for further professions (Guo, 2015). The use of digital technology in the mathematics classroom has long been a topic for consideration by mathematics lecturers. Digital technology tools in mathematics include: portable, graphic calculator and computerized graphics, specialized software, programmable toys or floor robots, spreadsheets and databases. Access to technology via personal devices will increase, with the consequence that technology integration into mathematics education, within and outside the classroom, can be easily realized. Students will also have personal technology such as a tablet, a smart watch, a mobile phone or similar with which they are familiar to use mathematical focused applications. These tools are allowing pupils to collect data, and manipulate it using spreadsheets and databases for work in numeracy (Moseley, 2009). The use of digital tools in mathematics speeds up the graphing process, freeing people to analyze and reflect on the relationships between data (Hennessy, 2010). Mathematical specialists' software such as Computer Algebra System (CAS), Dynamic Geometry System (DGS), Matrix Laboratory (Mat Lab), Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and so on. With the advent of such technology, the question arises as to what the impact on education and teaching practices should be in order to prepare the next generation of students for future careers (Clark-Wilson, 2015).

Digital technology has the ability to assist Mathematics teachers in improving the study and teaching of mathematics elsewhere. Students' mathematical performance has transformed due to their increased mathematical exposure (Cahyono & Ludwig, 2018). Teachers' greater use of digital materials will create a fresh experience for students learning mathematics, such as guaranteeing students are not bored (Wijaya et al., 2022).

Statement of the Problem

The national politics determines the quality of education policies, programmes and processes and eventually the products (results or outcomes). Government's underfunding and commoditization of education is likely to worsen the crisis in digital technology in education. Teachers encounter some challenges in the use of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning. While some of the barriers are extrinsic that is external to the teacher some of the barriers are intrinsic arising from the teacher's attitude, beliefs and knowledge. The external barriers arise mainly from institutional challenges in the acquisition of digital technology equipment. If the school does not provide adequate computers and other digital resources, and

lacks fast internet connection it becomes difficult to implement. Challenges internal to the teacher include challenges of inadequate training. Teachers need the skills and knowledge to be able to use technology in teaching, without which they lack the confidence in using it. These had negative effects on teachers and students. Therefore, concerned with this phenomenon, the study was conducted to find a way to incorporate digital technology in the teaching and learning of mathematics for global competitiveness at senior secondary school in Oshimili South local government area of Delta State

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to find a way to incorporate digital technology in the teaching and learning of mathematics for global competitiveness at senior secondary school in Oshimili South local government area of Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the availability of digital technologies to mathematics teachers for global competitiveness
2. Find out the Challenges encountered in the use of digital Technology in mathematics teaching and Learning for global competitiveness.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What digital technologies are available to mathematics teachers for global competitiveness?
2. What are the challenges of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness?

Hypothesis

The following null and alternative hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the mean responses scores of male and female teachers on availability of digital technologies to mathematics teachers and the challenges encountered by teachers as a result the use of digital technology in Mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness.

H₁: There is significant difference between the mean responses scores of male and female teachers on availability of digital technologies to mathematics teachers and the challenges encountered by teachers as a result the use of digital technology in mathematics teaching and Learning for global competitiveness.

Methodology

Design of the Study

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, since the opinion of the respondents were collected from the field

Population of the Study

The target population was all the all the senior secondary schools in Oshimili North educational zone of Delta State

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used for the study comprises of a sample size 160 respondents which is made up of twenty students each were randomly from each of the eight schools selected for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The respondents were requested to express their opinions on a 4-point modified Likert response scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with their weight ranging from 4-1 for positively skewed items and vice-versa for negatively skewed items. The instrument was validated by two experts who certified them fit for the study with a reliability coefficient of 0.74.

Analysis and Results of the Study

Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations and t-test statistics to test the hypothesis. The results of the study were obtained from the research questions answered through data collected analyzed. Any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above was adjudged to agree, while item with a mean score below 2.50 is adjudged to disagree.

Research Question 1: What digital technologies are available to mathematics

teachers for global competitiveness?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Results on the Availability of Digital Technologies to Mathematics Teachers for global competitiveness.

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	DECISION
1.	Not enough or limited access to computer hardware	101	54	5	0	3.60	0.55	Agree
2.	Non availability of computer software	86	62	10	2	3.45	0.63	Agree
3.	Lack of time in the school schedule for projects involving digital technology	80	59	19	2	3.36	0.72	Agree
4.	Lack of adequate technical support for digital technology projects	59	58	27	16	3.00	0.97	Agree
5.	Lack of knowledge about ways to integrate digital technology to enhance curriculum	82	46	13	19	3.20	1.03	Agree
6.	Digital technology integration is not a school priority	85	34	22	19	3.15	1.07	Agree
7.	Difficult finding substitutes in order for teachers attend training	51	45	46	18	2.81	1.01	Agree
8.	Students do not have access to the necessary technology at home	59	66	26	9	3.09	0.88	Agree
9.	Lecturers do not have access to the necessary technology at home	56	77	19	8	3.13	0.81	Agree
10.	Integrating and using different digital technology in a single lesson	85	54	11	10	3.14	0.86	Agree
11.	Inadequate training of Teachers in the use of digital technology	120	32	5	3	3.68	0.63	Agree
	Grand Mean and Standard Deviation					3.24	0.82	

The results obtained from Table 1 shows that all items were agreed with a grand mean and standard deviation scores of 3.24 and 0.83 respectively. This implies that the availability of digital technologies to mathematics teachers for global competitiveness were not enough or limited access to computer hardware for effective education

delivery and lack of adequate technical support for digital technology projects among others in Osimili North Local Government Area of Delta States of Nigeria

Research Question 2. What are the challenges of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness?

Table 2: Mean and standard Deviation Results on the Challenges Encountered by Teachers in the Use of Digital Technology in Mathematics Teaching and Learning for global competitiveness.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD	DECISION
1.	Lacks of fast internet connection	106	48	6	0	3.63	0.57	Agree
2.	Inadequate computers and other digital resources,	96	58	6	0	3.56	0.78	Agree
3.	Inadequate training of Teachers in the use of technology	86	48	23	3	3.36	0.80	Agree
4.	Inadequate staff training through workshops and conferences.	74	51	26	9	3.19	0.91	Agree
5.	Inadequate grant to schools for effective digital technology equipment	86	55	3	16	3.32	0.94	Agree
6.	Lack of experience in the use digital technologies	102	26	13	19	3.32	1.06	Agree
7.	Digital technology may be distracting to students	51	51	32	26	2.80	1.07	Agree
8.	Digital technology may disconnect students from face to face interactions.	67	74	16	3	3.28	0.73	Agree
9.	Digital technology may make cheating easier for students	58	80	13	9	3.17	0.82	Agree
10.	Digital technology may disadvantage certain students	93	45	13	9	3.38	0.87	Agree
11.	Inadequate training of Teachers in the use	99	54	7	0	3.58	0.57	Agree
	Grand Mean and Standard Deviation					3.33	0.82	

The results obtained from Table 2 shows that the grand mean and standard deviation for the respondents were 3.33 and 0.82 respectively. The table also shows that all items were agreed with mean scores ranging from 2.80 to 3.58. This implies that the items posed challenges to

teachers as a result of lack of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness.

Table 3: Independent Sample t-test Analysis on the Mean Responses of Male and Female Teachers on the Incorporation of Digital Technology in Mathematics Teaching and Learning for global competitiveness.

Gender	(N)	Mean	STD	df	t _{cal}	t _{cri}	A	Significance
Female	80	3.34	0.83	160	0.864	1.98	0.05	Reject H ₀
Male	80	3.33	0.82					

Table 3 reveals the mean responses of the male and female teachers on the incorporation of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness. The result shows that t_{cal} score of 0.864 which is less than t_{cri} score of 1.98 means the null hypothesis (H₀) should be rejected. Hence, the alternative hypothesis should be accepted. Therefore, it is clear from the result that there is significant difference between the mean responses score of male and female teachers on availability of digital technologies to mathematics teachers and the challenges encountered by teachers as a result the use of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study as presented in Table 1 indicate that the lack of availability of digital technology has drastically affected mathematics teaching and learning in education sector which were strongly agreed by the teachers as a result of not enough or limited access to computer hardware for effective education delivery and Lack of adequate technical support for digital technology projects among others. This is in agreement with Taylor (2021) who reported that digital technology offers new avenues of meaningful communication and collaboration between teachers and students and lack of funds for the purchase of new technology-assisted

learning tools such as mobile devices, interactive white boards, smart boards, tablets, laptops, simulations, dynamic visualization and virtual laboratories hardware stands out as the number one problem confronting the teaching and learning of Mathematics.

The result of the analysis in Table 2 shows the challenges of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness. This finding is in agreement with Haleem et al (2022) that integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience, allowing them to remain more interested in the subject without being distracted. They express that many teachers lack of knowledge about ways to integrate digital technology to enhance the curriculum and to integrate and use different digital tools in a single class session. These conditions bring about divided attention and poor concentration on the teaching job thereby reducing their output. Some become unnecessarily harsh to students and would not take time to give proper explanation on any concept taught using digital technology, as students' lose interest in class activities thereby affecting the impartation of such knowledge.

The result of the analysis in Table 3 reveals the mean responses of the male and female teachers on the impact of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness. In addition, higher number of respondent agreed that the alternative hypothesis should be accepted. Therefore, it is clear from the result that there is significant difference between the mean responses scores of male and female teachers on availability of digital technologies mathematics teachers and the challenges encountered by teachers as a result the use of digital technology in mathematics teaching and learning for global competitiveness.

The purchase of new digital technology infrastructures slowed down in pace which made learning atmosphere to be non-conducive for effective learning. Digital technology has the

ability to assist teachers in improving the study and teaching of mathematics elsewhere. Students' mathematical performance has transformed due to their increased mathematical exposure (Cahyono & Ludwig, 2018). Teachers' greater use of digital materials will create a fresh experience for students learning mathematics, such as guaranteeing students are not bored (Wijaya et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The main challenges in today's education system hindering institutions, students and their teachers from being internationally and globally competitive stem from issues of quality in education. Sustainable development goals emphasize quality education as one of the global goals. Digital technology is a gateway to the world for today's student and when applied in Mathematics teaching and learning will equip students with skills and knowledge relevant in today's world. Digital technology is needed to promote learning and position our students to be globally competitive. The digital transformation needed in today's world became more evident during the COVID-19 pandemic which accelerated the need to rapidly adopt digital solution. In the 2022 edition of the networked readiness index comparing nations and their economies, highest ranked economies were committed to ensuring that technologies are accessible, affordable and beneficial for the economy and the society at large. Digital learning being an instructional practice that effectively uses technology to strengthen a student's learning experience and encompasses a wide spectrum of tools and practices remain the key to promoting learning in the Mathematics education sector for sustainable national development and global competitiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the above, the following recommendations were made:

1. Digital technology should be used in teacher education and in the professional development of teachers' training and retraining programme.
2. Government should provide the necessary funds to schools for the purchase of digital technology facilities like computer hardware for effective education delivery.
3. The Mathematics teacher should use digital resources like apps, social media etc to keep the class informed about activities and upcoming assignments
4. There is need for adequate provision of equipment and infrastructures by the government for Mathematics teachers to perform their duties diligently.
5. Focus your technology-based lessons on teaching your students digital citizenship or skills that will help them thoughtfully and effectively navigate digital media. Broadly defined, digital citizenship is the safe, ethical, informed and responsible use of technology.

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